

ACTIVITIES OF MODERN MOVEMENTS AND POLITICAL ORGANIZATIONS IN TURKESTAN

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The modern progressive movement that emerged in Turkestan in the late 19th - early 20th centuries occupies an important place in the centuries-old history of the Uzbek people. Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, Ubaydulla Khojaev, Obidjon Mahmudov, Fitrat, Cholpon, Saidnosir Mirjalilov and others took the first step towards uniting the local people under the banner of national independence, seizing power and establishing a national Uzbek state. Using the existing historical conditions, they created educational societies such as "Turon", "Imdodiya" and national political organizations such as "Shurai Islam", "Turk Adam Markaziyat".

At the same time, the progressives dealt with important issues related to the fate of the people and the country, and tried to open the closed eyes of the people, to educate them in the spirit of respect for great historical values such as freedom, freedom and independence. They urged the nation to fight to break the shackles of colonialism. In this way, the Jadids raised public education to the primary level as the most reliable tool of development. Due to the lack of higher education institutions in Turkestan, modern progressives paid special attention to the issue of educating young people abroad, especially introducing them to the achievements of European science.

On May 12, 1909, the "Jamiyati Khairiya" organization of Turkestan Jadids, which was first established in Tashkent, led the education of students abroad. With his support, young people began to be sent to study in higher schools and madrasas in the cities of Petersburg, Saratov, Kazan, Ufa, Orenburg, as well as in foreign cities such as Istanbul and Cairo.

"Tarbiyai atfol" society of modernists formed on July 18, 1909 in the city of Bukhara sent many young people to study in Istanbul, such as Fitrat, Osmankhoja Polathoja son, Ato Khoja, Mazhar Burkhanov. The number of students sent from Bukhara to study abroad was increased to 15 in 1911 and 30 in 1912. Later, writers and scholars such as Fitrat, Ghazi Olim Yunusov, Khalid Said, Eson Efandi Musaev, mature

lawyers such as Mustafa Choqayev, Ubaidulla Khojaev, Norbotabekov emerged from among such students.

After the establishment of the Soviet regime in Turkestan, on April 21, 1918, Turkestan State University was opened in the new city of Tashkent under the leadership of A.V. Popov. Both the pedagogical team and students of this higher education institution consisted mainly of representatives of European nations. On May 12, 1918, Turkestan Muslim People's Children's School was opened in the old part of Tashkent under the leadership of Munavvar Qari Abdurashidkhanov for the children of local nationalities. In Samarkand, Mahmudhoja Behbudi also began to open a branch of this school. However, the Bolshevik government did not allow it. At that time, there were no secondary educational institutions in the country that could prepare students for admission to the Turkestan State University. As a result, the number of local youth among the students of the Turkestan State University was less than that of the Uzbek students in Moscow. For example, in the academic year 1920-21, only 2 out of 2,500 students of Turkestan University, 3 out of 200 students of Darul ilmi Sharqiya (Institute of Oriental Studies) were Uzbek children. there was not a single student¹.

This situation caused serious resistance of local intellectuals and youth, and the idea of training the existing students abroad was once again on the agenda. The Uzbek board of education was considered an important organization in the organization and management of education in the country. However, many artificial obstacles were placed by the authorities of the Soviet government to effectively launch its activities². Elbek informs the following about the issue of teaching students abroad: "In early 1921, a project was created by the Uzbek board of education to study abroad from Turkestan, and a list of several students was taken and submitted to the government, with the student being Sayyidalihjoja at the beginning. After several periods of this, when it became clear that our government would not be able to provide financial assistance, this matter stopped by itself. However, the passion for reading among the students did not end there. Some of the students who were more self-centered (although they sold their belongings) dreamed of going abroad again.

Said Ahmad Nazirov, the editor of "Armug'an" magazine, who later graduated from the Moscow Textile Institute, said in the interrogation report of December 24, 1930:

¹Irzayev B. Turkiston jadidlarining ko'mak tashkiloti. Toshkent.2016. B-4-5.

² Э л б е к. Ўзбек билим ҳайъати ва унинг ҳоли // Қизил байроқ. 1921 йил 1 октябрь., Э л б е к. Ўзбек элининг билим юртлари //Қизил байроқ. 1921 йил 21 декабрь.

"At the end of 1921, we studied at Rabfak in Tashkent. A struggle movement for studying abroad has appeared among students. Then two groups were formed. The 1st group is young people who want to study in Moscow and Leningrad, and the 2nd group wants to study in Germany. Abduvasik Muhammedov and I led the group going to Moscow and Leningrad. Tolagan Momin, who was a teacher at the "Navoi" school in Tashkent, was the head of the youth going to Germany. He remembers that all of us were united by the "Ko'mak" organization and the great dream of serving the country.

In the message signed by Gazi Yunus, "Student of Barak Khan", the Bukhara People's Republic took over the sponsorship of some Turkestan students at the request of the "Ko'mak" association. In particular, Bukhara writes that he paid the money of two students (Sayyidalikhoja and Ahmad Shukuri - the author) and promised for two more students (Sattar Jabbar and Vali Qayyumkhan - the author). He thanked the government of Bukhara on behalf of Turkestan and called on everyone to rush to help "Ko'mak" association³.

Usmonkhan Eshonhojaev said: "Many of the students who went to study in Berlin from Turkestan, Bukhara, with the support of various institutions, some of them left with enough for one year's supply at most. Some students have taken a very small, even dry "risk" route. It is well-known that the result of the World War greatly disrupted the economic situation of Germany. There, as in our country, the market prices are rising hourly, and the value of the white is decreasing day by day. All over Turkestan, our people, community workers, and responsible workers should take various measures and take any necessary measures.

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³ Бароқхонталабаси. Шарафлик "Қўмак" // Қизил байроқ. 1922 йил 22 июль.

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